

ANALYSIS OF THE ANTIRADICAL ACTIVITY OF THE AS-AN FOOD SUPPLEMENT

Askarov Ibrohimjon Rahmonovich

Professor, Department of Chemistry, Andijan State University;
Doctor of Chemical Sciences;

Honored Inventor of Uzbekistan; Chairman of the Academy of
Traditional Medicine of Uzbekistan

Hakimov Nasrulla Sabirovich

Associate Professor, Department of Medical Radiology,
Oncology and Phthisiology,

Andijan State Medical Institute; Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences

Noibzhonova Khurshidabonu Murodjon kizi

Assistant, Department of Medical Chemistry, Andijan State Medical
Institute

E-mail: knoibzhonova@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17837208>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 27th November 2025

Accepted: 28th November 2025

Online: 29th November 2025

KEYWORDS

antiradical activity, DPPH, AS-AN, flavonoid, antioxidant, free radical.

ABSTRACT

It is well known that almost all nations of the world have traditionally used medicinal plants for treating various diseases since ancient times. Medicinal plants were widely applied in the medical practices of ancient civilizations such as Assyria, Egypt, China, India, and Rome, as well as in medieval Arab countries, Central Asia, Armenia, Georgia, and Europe.

*In this study, the antiradical properties of a plant-based food supplement called "AS-AN," obtained from *Plantago (zubtutum)* leaves, were investigated against the stable free radical DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl). The results demonstrated that the aqueous extract exhibits the highest antiradical activity..*

Introduction. Various natural antioxidants — including spices, oils, teas, seeds, grains, cocoa husks, fruits, and vegetables — are widely used in food and medicine. Compounds such as ascorbic acid, tocopherols, carotenoids, flavonoids (quercetin, kaempferol, myricetin), catechins (carnosol, rosmanol, rosamiridiphenol), polyphenols and phenolic acids are known to possess high antioxidant activity.

Based on this, the antiradical activity (ARA) of the AS-AN extract was investigated using the stable free radical **DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl)**.

Materials and Methods. DPPH Assay. To evaluate antiradical activity, we used a spectrophotometric method based on measuring the kinetics of reduction of the stable DPPH radical by antioxidants.

- A 5×10^{-4} M standard DPPH solution in ethanol acidified with acetic acid was prepared.
- The solution was diluted 1:10 with ethanol to obtain a working solution.
- The optical density at 517 nm was adjusted to not exceed 0.9.
- To 5 mL of the DPPH working solution, 50 μ L of the plant extract was added.

- The decrease in optical density was recorded at 517 nm for 30 minutes.
- A DPPH working solution without extract served as the control.

Calculation of Antiradical Activity.

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{control}}} \times 100\%$$

Where:

- **A_{sample}** – absorbance of the test sample,
- **A_{control}** – absorbance of the control solution.

Results and Discussion. Since antioxidants may act through different mechanisms, evaluating their activity using multiple methods is recommended. In this study, the ARA of AS-AN extracts was assessed based on their interaction with the DPPH radical.

When the AS-AN extract was added, the characteristic purple color of the DPPH solution faded, indicating conversion of the free radical to a non-radical form. A sharp decrease in optical density confirmed strong antiradical activity. Because the extract showed very high activity, it was diluted 1:100 using DMSO.

Optical Density Changes Over Time

Extract	Optical density, D	Time, min	Concentration
As-AN	0.1	30	0.07
As-AN	0.2		0.18
As-AN	0.3	25	0.26
As-AN	0.4		0.35
As-AN	0.5	20	0.40
As-AN	0.6		0.51
As-AN	0.7	15	0.56
As-AN	0.8		0.64
As-AN	0.9	10	0.76
As-AN	1.0		0.79
As-AN	1.1	5	0.88
As-AN	1.2		0.93
As-AN	1.3	0	1

The aqueous extract of AS-AN demonstrated the highest capacity for scavenging free radicals. To quantify antiradical activity, the DPPH assay and the t_{50} parameter were used. t_{50} represents the time required to reduce the initial radical concentration by 50%.

Table 1. IC₅₀ and t₅₀ Values

Extract	IC ₅₀ (μL)	t ₅₀ (s), for 50 μL
As-AN	9.9±0.69	67.4±3.45

A low IC₅₀ value (approximately 10 μL) indicates strong antiradical activity.

Conclusion. The antiradical activity of the aqueous extract of the AS-AN food supplement was investigated. Numerous publications report that plant extracts rich in polyphenols and flavonoids exhibit the strongest antioxidant effects. The present study confirmed that AS-AN possesses high antiradical potential:

- Rapid reduction of DPPH absorbance,
- Low IC₅₀ value,

- Moderate t_{50} time.

Further studies are needed to determine the qualitative and quantitative composition of AS-AN, including polyphenols, flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, and other active compounds, to better understand its mechanism of action.

References:

1. Trineeva O.V. Methods for determining antioxidant activity of plant and synthetic objects in pharmacy (review). *Drug Development and Registration*, 2017; (4): 180–197.
2. Melnichuk V.A. Rapid method for determination of antiradical activity of medicinal substances. *Chemical Pharmaceutical Journal*, 1985; 5: 565–567.
3. Seyoum A., Asres K., El-Fiky F.K. Structure–radical scavenging activity relationships of flavonoids. *Phytochemistry*, 2006; 67: 2058–2070.

